

SUPPORTING INFORMATION

Modelling Environmental Effects on Vibronic Spectra of Flexible Dyes from Simple Solvents to Solid Organic Matrices: Dystyrylbenzene as a Test Case.

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A QMD-FF

In the following are reported some details concerning the calculations related to QMD-FF parameterization. Conversely, in the next sections, more information concerning the MD runs (B) or the calculation of the spectral lineshapes will be given (C).

A.1 Target chromophore

The parameterization of a Quantum Mechanically Derived Force-Filed (QMD-FF) has been performed on the DSB oligophenylenevinylene, shown in Figure S1. The same parameterization procedure has been followed for both the ground S_0 and the excited S_1 state.

Figure S1: DSB molecule. The atom types employed in the parameterization protocol are shown together with the definition of the two flexible dihedrals (δ_1 and δ_2) and the stiff one (ϕ), governing the rotation around the C=C central bond. The same atom types were employed in both S_0 and S_1 parameterizations.

A.2 QM data

Unless otherwise stated, all QM calculations to build the reference QMD-FF databases were carried out with the GAUSSIAN16 code [1], at DFT level, using the CAM-B3LYP functional, with the 6-31+G(d,p) basis set. The ground state optimized geometry, found through a QM global minimization is shown in Figure S1. Additionally, the Hessian matrix and vibrational frequencies were computed at such optimized conformation. By looking at the resulting frequencies, it appears that, despite the extended conjugation, a certain degree of flexibility should be expected, in particular for the rotation around the phenylene–vinylene bonds. Indeed, the δ_1 and δ_2 dihedrals shown in Figure S1 should be considered flexible, in the sense that significant amplitude distortions from the equilibrium position should be expected, and the harmonic approximation could fail. For each of the aforementioned dihedrals, a relaxed internal energy scan was performed, by optimizing all degrees of freedom except the scanned torsional angle. Moreover, as DSB’s flexibility is expected to become enhanced upon electronic transition, a relaxed scan of the internal energy as a function of the rotation around the vinylene $Cv_1=Cv_2$ bond was also carried out. Finally, the same database was retrieved for the S_1 excited state, by performing the same calculations as TD-DFT level, using the same functional/basis set employed for S_0 .

A.3 QMD-FF parameterization

The QMD-FF was obtained by means of the JOYCE parameterization protocol [2–4], as outlined in the following. It is worth mentioning that the very same procedure is applied to both states considered.

- i) Assign specific atomic types, based on symmetry and chemical equivalence considerations as shown in Figure S1
- ii) Obtain the inter-molecular parameters (Lennard-Jones and point charges) that govern the solute-environment interaction.
- iii) Assign a suitable set of internal coordinates (ICs) to the solute, to mimic its intra-molecular dynamics

- iv) Obtain the intra-molecular parameters (force-constants and equilibrium ICs), assigned to the chosen IC set

A.3.1 DSB QMD-FF Atom types

A complete list of the chosen atom types, displayed in Figure S1, is given in Table S1, together with their inter-molecular parameters. Concretely, eight different atom-types were used for Carbon, and six for Hydrogen.

Atom type	σ	ϵ	$q (S_0)$	$q (S_1)$
Cb ₁	3.55	0.2929	-0.100582	-0.091539
Cb ₂	3.55	0.2929	-0.186905	-0.190693
Cb ₃	3.55	0.2929	-0.085670	-0.090004
Cb ₄	3.55	0.2929	0.037663	0.063603
Cb ₅	3.55	0.2929	-0.191756	-0.219691
Cb ₆	3.55	0.2929	-0.163658	-0.175232
Cv ₁	3.55	0.3180	0.045449	0.091647
Cv ₂	3.55	0.3180	-0.139514	-0.156196
Hb ₁	2.42	0.1255	0.127873	0.124402
Hb ₂	2.42	0.1255	0.141831	0.142822
Hb ₃	2.42	0.1255	0.113015	0.113742
Hb ₆	2.42	0.1255	0.126210	0.127759
Hv ₁	2.42	0.1255	0.155272	0.156531
Hv ₂	2.42	0.1255	0.151803	0.155419

Table S1: Intermolecular parameters employed for DSB: σ (Å), ϵ (kJ/mol) and q (e⁻, for ground and excited state, respectively) Atom types are shown in Figure S1

A.3.2 Embedding FF Atom types

Figure S2: Atom types employed for *n*-tetradecane (left) and PHTP (right).

<i>n</i> -tetradecane				PHTP			
Atom type	σ	ϵ	q	Atom type	σ	ϵ	q
C_T	3.500	0.2761	-0.1800	C_1	3.500	0.2761	-0.0600
C_2	3.500	0.2761	-0.1200	C_2	3.500	0.2761	-0.1200
H_C	2.500	0.1255	-0.0060	C_3	3.500	0.2761	-0.1200
H_2	2.500	0.1255	-0.0060	H_1	2.500	0.1255	0.0600
				H_2	2.500	0.1255	0.0600
				H_3	2.500	0.1255	0.0600

Table S2: Intermolecular parameters transferred from the OPLS database [5, 6] to describe *n*-tetradecane (left) and PHTP (right). σ (Å), ϵ (kJ/mol) and q (e^-) Atom types are shown in Figure S2.

A.3.3 DSB Intra-molecular QMD-FF

The intra-molecular energy term E_{QMD-FF}^{intra} parameterization has been derived from the QM database (equilibrium geometry and its Hessian matrix, relaxed torsional energy scans) discussed in section A.2 by means of the JOYCE code. The parameterization procedure is outlined in following:

- The atom types for the intra-molecular term are defined (see Figure S1 and Table S1) according to symmetry and/or chemical equivalence, yet leaving a high degree of specificity which should allow for accurate parameterizations. It is worth stressing that the same atom types are employed for both considered states.
- As far as the employed ICs are concerned, all possible stretching and bending coordinates were included in the QMD-FF description. Moreover, several stiff dihedrals defined by quadruplets of heavy atoms were included in the FF, as the one ruling the planarity of the C=C double bonds and of the aromatic rings. In addition, based on the normal mode analysis of the QM hessian, a supplementary pseudo-stretching coordinate was introduced, defined as the distance R_{ht} between the head and tail carbon of the DSB molecule. Finally, the chain flexible dihedrals (δ_n , see Figure S1), defined through a single quadruplet of connected atoms, were also added to the ICs collection.
- A model potential function is assigned to each IC, following the standard JOYCE criteria. Concretely, harmonic potentials are employed for all stretching, pseudo-stretching, bending and stiff torsion ICs, while Fourier-like sums are employed for the flexible dihedrals. The same model functions were employed for both states, although it is possible to assign different functional forms to the same IC, depending on the considered state. This is for instance the strategy used when parameterizing excited states of conjugated chains, where the σ/π character of two neighbouring bonds is exchanged upon transitions. In such cases one can switch from an harmonic form to a Fourier-like series and vice-versa. In the present case, a preliminary parameterization which employs an harmonic potential for the ϕ angle for both states will be first attempted.

- The usual two-step procedure was adopted: a first JOYCE cycle which fits all harmonic parameters at once and a second cycle, in which the harmonic parameters are fixed according to the Frozen Internal Rotation Approximation, [2] and the parameters for the flexible dihedral are parameterized against the QM torsional relaxed energy scans. Since the reference QM data are not the same, two different sets of parameters, assigned to the same collection of atom types/ICs, should be expected for the two electronic states.

As mentioned above, according to the JOYCE approach, the ICs chosen to represent the target molecule dynamics can be further classified into two different sets: stiff or flexible, depending whether rather small displacements from the equilibrium geometry or large amplitude motions are to be expected. E_{QMD-FF}^{intra} is therefore further partitioned in several contributions, namely

$$E_{QMD-FF}^{intra} = E_s + E_b + E_{st} + E_{ft} + E_{Nb}^{intra} \quad (S1)$$

The first three terms refer to stiff IC, and can be approximated through harmonic potentials, *i.e.*

$$E_s = \frac{1}{2} \sum_s^{N_s} k_s (r - r^0)^2 ; E_b = \frac{1}{2} \sum_b^{N_b} k_b (\theta - \theta^0)^2 ; E_{st} = \frac{1}{2} \sum_{st}^{N_{st}} k_{st} (\phi - \phi^0)^2 \quad (S2)$$

It is worth noticing that while the first two terms, *i.e.* the stretching and bending contributions E_s and E_b , are widely used by popular FFs, the third expression (E_{st}) is seldom employed for describing torsions of stiff dihedral angles in standard approaches. Yet, it appears to be better suited to account for the internal energy due to small and fast distortions of a dihedral ϕ from its equilibrium position ϕ_i^0 . The JOYCE procedure routinely employs the E_{st} term, to mimic the behaviour of a stiff and fast vibrating torsion, as those ruling the planarity of aromatic rings or conjugated double bonds or the octahedral symmetry of a metal-organic complex.

The last two terms of equation (S1) are instead assigned to flexible ICs, which are expected to experience larger distortion during simulation. In fact, the term

$$E_{ft} = \sum_{\mu}^{N_{ft}} \sum_j^{N_{cos\mu}} k_{j\mu}^{ft} [1 + \cos(n_j^{\mu} \delta_{\mu} - \gamma_j^{\mu})] \quad (S3)$$

(where δ_μ is the μ -th flexible torsion, $k_{j\mu}^{st}$ its force constant, n_j^μ the multiplicity and γ_j^μ a proper phase), is devised to describe the large amplitude displacements induced by a flexible dihedral, as those defining, for instance, the rotation around a σ bond. Finally, the last term of equation (S1), contains the non-bonded intra-molecular interactions, implemented as a sum of electrostatic charge-charge and Lennard-Jones (LJ) terms, expressed as

$$E_{Nb}^{intra} = \sum_i \sum_{i < j} \frac{q_i^{intra} q_j^{intra}}{r_{ij}} + \sum_i \sum_{i < j} 4\epsilon_{ij}^{intra} \left[\left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}^{intra}}{r_{ij}} \right)^{12} - \left(\frac{\sigma_{ij}^{intra}}{r_{ij}} \right)^6 \right] \quad (\text{S4})$$

where $q_{i(j)}^{intra}$ is the point charge on atom $i(j)$ and r_{ij} the distance between atoms i and j belonging to the same molecule. In most popular transferable FFs the non-bonded contributions are counted among all possible pairs of interacting sites $i-j$, adopting the same set of LJ and charge parameters for both inter-molecular and intra-molecular interactions. Conversely, the JOYCE protocol allows for a more specific parameterization, where both intra-molecular charge and LJ parameters may be in principle different from the ones adopted for the description of inter-molecular interactions and they can be included in the QMD-FF just for selected intra-molecular atom pairs. In the DSB case, no intra-molecular interactions of this kind were allowed.

Once the FF functional form and the underlying IC's collection have been selected, a complete set of QMD-FF parameters is retrieved through the JOYCE code by minimizing the functional

$$I^{intra} = \sum_{K < L}^{3N-6} \frac{2W_{KL}''}{C} \left[H_{KL} - \left(\frac{\partial^2 E_{FF}^{intra}}{\partial Q_K \partial Q_L} \right)_{g_0} \right]^2 + \sum_g^{N_{geom}} W_g [\Delta U_g - E_g^{intra}]^2 \quad (\text{S5})$$

In the first term on the right side of equation (S5), the sum runs over the $3N-6$ dye's coordinates, C is a normalization factor, Q_K is the K^{th} normal mode, whereas H_{KL} and $\frac{\partial^2 E_{FF}^{intra}}{\partial Q_K \partial Q_L}$ are QM and FF Hessian matrix elements, both evaluated in the minimum energy geometry (g_0). The normalized diagonal elements of the weight matrix \mathbf{W}'' are set, as in previous applications, at twice the value of those corresponding to the off diagonal terms. In the second term, ΔU_g is the QM computed energy difference between the the g and g_0 geometries and N_{geom} is the number of the different geometrical arrangements sampled for each target molecule. The weights W_g are all initially set the same value.

For both considered states, the JOYCE parameterization was eventually carried out on a

system of 247 redundant ICs, by minimizing the objective function (S5) as function of 71 independent parameters, obtaining a final standard deviation of 0.02 kJ/mol and of 0.21 kJ/mol for the S_0 and S_1 state, respectively. The QMD-FF parameters are reported in detail in Tables S3-S11 for both states.

A.3.4 DSB QMD-FF parameters

S₀

stretching	r ⁰	k ^s stretching	r ⁰	k ^s	
C _{B2} -C _{B1}	1.391	3486.03	C _{B3} -C _{B2}	1.390	3449.90
C _{B3} -C _{B4}	1.401	3090.03	C _{B5} -C _{B6}	1.402	3139.35
C _{B6} -C _{B6}	1.385	3488.39	C _{B4} -C _{V1}	1.469	2687.81
C _{V2} -C _{B5}	1.467	2628.29	C _{V1} -C _{V2}	1.341	4695.79
C _{B1} -H _{B1}	1.085	3418.62	C _{B2} -H _{B2}	1.085	3386.17
C _{B3} -H _{B3}	1.086	3372.98	C _{B6} -H _{B6}	1.087	3383.84
C _{V1} -H _{V1}	1.088	3319.84	C _{V2} -H _{V2}	1.088	3327.26
R _{ht}	16.146	405.87			

Table S3: Intramolecular stretching parameters for DSB in its S₀ state: equilibrium distances r⁰ are in Å and force constants k^s in kJ/mol Å⁻². The pseudo-stretching IC, R_{ht}, indicated the C_{B1}-C_{B1} head-tail distance.

bending	θ ⁰	k ^b	bending	θ ⁰	k ^b
C _{B2} -C _{B1} -C _{B2}	119.4	578.58	C _{B3} -C _{B2} -C _{B1}	120.0	652.08
C _{B2} -C _{B3} -C _{B4}	121.3	682.80	C _{B3} -C _{B4} -C _{B3}	117.9	479.77
C _{B6} -C _{B5} -C _{B6}	117.3	466.38	C _{B5} -C _{B6} -C _{B6}	121.8	681.87
C _{B3} -C _{B4} -C _{V1}	118.6	528.78	C _{B6} -C _{B5} -C _{V2}	123.8	463.45
C _{B4} -C _{V1} -C _{V2}	126.9	435.19	C _{B5} -C _{V2} -C _{V1}	126.8	425.83
C _{B2} -C _{B1} -H _{B1}	120.4	328.04	C _{B1} -C _{B2} -H _{B2}	120.2	331.81
C _{B3} -C _{B2} -H _{B2}	119.8	337.48	C _{B2} -C _{B3} -H _{B3}	119.0	361.06
C _{B4} -C _{B3} -H _{B3}	119.1	302.40	C _{B5} -C _{B6} -H _{B6}	119.0	326.02
C _{B6} -C _{B6} -H _{B6}	119.2	355.10	C _{B4} -C _{V1} -H _{V1}	114.2	374.25
C _{B5} -C _{V2} -H _{V2}	114.2	388.33	C _{V2} -C _{V1} -H _{V1}	118.9	242.17

Table S4: Intramolecular bending parameters for DSB in its S₀ state: equilibrium angles θ⁰ are in degree force constants k^b in kJ/mol rad⁻².

dihedral	ϕ^0	k^t	dihedral	ϕ^0	k^t
$C_{B3}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}-C_{B2}$	0.0	53.15	$C_{B1}-C_{B2}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}$	0.0	71.64
$C_{B2}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{B3}$	0.0	55.85	$C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}-C_{B5}$	0.0	62.94
$C_{B6}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}$	0.0	58.98	$C_{B2}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{V1}$	180.0	56.62
$C_{V2}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}$	180.0	67.72	$C_{V1}-C_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}$	0.0	235.20
$C_{B1}-C_{B2}-C_{B2}-C_{V1}$	180.0	62.53	$C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}-C_{V2}$	0.0	86.83
$C_{B3}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}-H_{B1}$	180.0	62.53	$C_{B4}-C_{B3}-C_{B2}-H_{B2}$	180.0	66.82
$H_{B2}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}-C_{B2}$	180.0	60.59	$H_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}$	180.0	64.53
$H_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{B3}$	180.0	56.40	$C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}-H_{B6}$	180.0	62.21
$C_{B6}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}-H_{B6}$	180.0	60.12	$H_{B2}-C_{B1}-C_{B3}-C_{B2}$	0.0	109.53
$H_{B3}-C_{B2}-C_{B4}-C_{B3}$	0.0	116.14	$H_{B1}-C_{B2}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}$	0.0	93.91
$H_{V2}-C_{V1}-C_{B5}-C_{V2}$	0.0	137.62	$C_{V1}-C_{B4}-C_{V2}-H_{V1}$	0.0	140.49
$H_{B2}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}-H_{B1}$	0.0	32.70	$H_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B2}-H_{B2}$	0.0	33.77
$H_{B6}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}-H_{B6}$	0.0	37.02	$H_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{V1}$	0.0	28.89
$C_{V2}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}-H_{B6}$	0.0	38.70	$C_{B4}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-C_{B5}$	180.0	126.99
$H_{V1}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-H_{V2}$	180.0	92.00	$H_{V1}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-C_{B5}$	0.0	66.23

Table S5: Intramolecular parameters for stiff torsions for DSB in its S_0 state: equilibrium dihedral angles ϕ^0 are in degrees and force constants k^t in kJ/mol rad^{-2} . The ϕ dihedral is defined by the $C_{b4}-C_{v1}-C_{v2}-C_{b5}$, $H_{v1}-C_{v1}-C_{v2}-H_{v2}$ and $H_{v1}-C_{v1}-C_{v2}-C_{b5}$ quadruplets.

dihedral	N_{cos}	n	k^d (kJ/mol)	γ (degr)
$C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}$ (δ_1)	3	0	0.953	0.00
		2	-4.000	0.00
		4	1.041	0.00
$C_{V1}-C_{V2}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}$ (δ_2)	3	0	0.953	0.00
		2	4.222	180.00
		4	1.045	0.00

Table S6: Intramolecular parameters for flexible torsions for DSB in its S_0 state: number of cosines n , γ (degrees) and force constants k^d in kJ/mol .

S₁

stretching	r ⁰	k ^s stretching	r ⁰	k ^s	
C _{B2} -C _{B1}	1.397	3392.03	C _{B3} -C _{B2}	1.383	3540.80
C _{B3} -C _{B4}	1.415	2973.17	C _{B5} -C _{B6}	1.426	2725.44
C _{B6} -C _{B6}	1.366	3818.40	C _{B4} -C _{V1}	1.435	2801.42
C _{V2} -C _{B5}	1.415	2973.50	C _{V1} -C _{V2}	1.382	3636.06
C _{B1} -H _{B1}	1.085	3425.91	C _{B2} -H _{B2}	1.086	3382.16
C _{B3} -H _{B3}	1.086	3389.78	C _{B6} -H _{B6}	1.087	3409.12
C _{V1} -H _{V1}	1.086	3335.24	C _{V2} -H _{V2}	1.087	3323.73
R _{ht}	16.051	413.25			

Table S7: Intramolecular stretching parameters for DSB in its S₁ state: equilibrium distances r⁰ are in Å and force constants k^s in kJ/mol Å⁻².

bending	θ ⁰	k ^b	bending	θ ⁰	k ^b
C _{B2} -C _{B1} -C _{B2}	119.4	598.60	C _{B3} -C _{B2} -C _{B1}	120.2	637.23
C _{B2} -C _{B3} -C _{B4}	121.5	636.50	C _{B3} -C _{B4} -C _{B3}	117.3	477.86
C _{B6} -C _{B5} -C _{B6}	116.8	532.11	C _{B5} -C _{B6} -C _{B6}	122.3	568.14
C _{B3} -C _{B4} -C _{V1}	119.1	577.31	C _{B6} -C _{B5} -C _{V2}	123.5	406.97
C _{B4} -C _{V1} -C _{V2}	126.3	524.91	C _{B5} -C _{V2} -C _{V1}	126.1	633.92
C _{B2} -C _{B1} -H _{B1}	120.3	300.21	C _{B1} -C _{B2} -H _{B2}	120.0	327.23
C _{B3} -C _{B2} -H _{B2}	119.8	340.77	C _{B2} -C _{B3} -H _{B3}	119.1	340.30
C _{B4} -C _{B3} -H _{B3}	118.7	285.06	C _{B5} -C _{B6} -H _{B6}	118.2	327.22
C _{B6} -C _{B6} -H _{B6}	119.5	328.81	C _{B4} -C _{V1} -H _{V1}	115.2	343.44
C _{B5} -C _{V2} -H _{V2}	115.4	283.53	C _{V2} -C _{V1} -H _{V1}	118.5	331.97

Table S8: Intramolecular bending parameters for DSB in its S₁ state: equilibrium angles θ⁰ are in degree force constants k^b in kJ/mol rad⁻².

dihedral	ϕ^0	k^t	dihedral	ϕ^0	k^t
$C_{B3}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}-C_{B2}$	0.0	48.86	$C_{B1}-C_{B2}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}$	0.0	72.37
$C_{B2}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{B3}$	0.0	44.71	$C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}-C_{B5}$	0.0	80.37
$C_{B6}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}$	0.0	38.00	$C_{B2}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{V1}$	180.0	43.11
$C_{V2}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}$	180.0	34.64	$C_{V1}-C_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}$	0.0	266.55
$C_{B1}-C_{B2}-C_{B2}-C_{V1}$	180.0	57.62	$C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}-C_{V2}$	0.0	79.64
$C_{B3}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}-H_{B1}$	180.0	57.62	$C_{B4}-C_{B3}-C_{B2}-H_{B2}$	180.0	70.72
$H_{B2}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}-C_{B2}$	180.0	56.49	$H_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}$	180.0	68.11
$H_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{B3}$	180.0	43.62	$C_{B5}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}-H_{B6}$	180.0	77.86
$C_{B6}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}-H_{B6}$	180.0	33.84	$H_{B2}-C_{B1}-C_{B3}-C_{B2}$	0.0	111.73
$H_{B3}-C_{B2}-C_{B4}-C_{B3}$	0.0	127.37	$H_{B1}-C_{B2}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}$	0.0	108.55
$H_{V2}-C_{V1}-C_{B5}-C_{V2}$	0.0	127.80	$C_{V1}-C_{B4}-C_{V2}-H_{V1}$	0.0	157.14
$H_{B2}-C_{B2}-C_{B1}-H_{B1}$	0.0	29.73	$H_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B2}-H_{B2}$	0.0	36.89
$H_{B6}-C_{B6}-C_{B6}-H_{B6}$	0.0	49.27	$H_{B3}-C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{V1}$	0.0	20.95
$C_{V2}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}-H_{B6}$	0.0	23.57	$C_{B4}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-C_{B5}$	180.0	80.31
$H_{V1}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-H_{V2}$	180.0	56.78	$H_{V1}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-C_{B5}$	0.0	38.01

Table S9: Intramolecular parameters for stiff torsions for DSB in its S_1 state: equilibrium dihedral angles ϕ^0 are in degrees and force constants k^t in kJ/mol rad^{-2} . The ϕ dihedral is defined by the $C_{B4}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-C_{B5}$, $H_{V1}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-H_{V2}$ and $H_{V1}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}-C_{B5}$ quadruplets.

dihedral	N_{cos}	n	k^d (kJ/mol)	γ (degr)
$C_{B3}-C_{B4}-C_{V1}-C_{V2}$	3	0	3.053	0.00
		2	-9.787	0.00
		4	1.496	0.00
$C_{V1}-C_{V2}-C_{B5}-C_{B6}$	3	0	3.053	0.00
		2	15.355	180.00
		4	2.308	0.00

Table S10: Intramolecular parameters for flexible torsions for DSB in its S_1 state: number of cosines n , γ (degrees) and force constants k^d in kJ/mol .

Pair (<i>ij</i>)	σ_{ij}^{intra}	ϵ_{ij}^{intra}
H _{B3} -H _{V1}	2.420	0.0500
H _{B3} -H _{V1}	2.420	0.0500
H _{V1} -H _{B3}	2.420	0.0500
H _{V1} -H _{B3}	2.420	0.0500
H _{V2} -H _{B6}	2.420	0.0500
H _{V2} -H _{B6}	2.420	0.0500
H _{B6} -H _{V2}	2.420	0.0500
H _{B6} -H _{V2}	2.420	0.0500

Table S11: Intramolecular parameters for non-bonded intramolecular interactions for DSB in its S₀ and S₁ state: σ^{intra} (Å) and ϵ^{intra} (kJ/mol).

A.3.5 DSB QMD-FF preliminary validation

In Figure S3.a, we first test the similarity of harmonic normal modes computed at each level for both S_0 and S_1 states of the DSB chromophore. As shown in this analysis, the MM vibrational

Figure S3: (a) Overlap of QM and MM (with the QMD-FF) normal modes (top) and correlation plot between QM and MM vibrational frequencies (bottom), for both S_0 and S_1 QMD-FFs; (b) Relaxed scan along flexible torsions corresponding to QM and MM potentials.

frequencies are very similar to the QM ones. Moreover, the overlap between QM and MM modes is generally large, supporting the validity of the FF. In particular, the quality of S_0 and S_1 FFs is similar, although, for S_0 , slightly larger overlaps are registered. In panel (b) of the same figure, we include the energy profiles associated with relaxed scans over the single bonds (δ_1 around the outer bond and δ_2 around the inner bond, see Figure S1) evaluated with QM methods and the QMD-FF.

B MD

B.1 Cooling strategies

To achieve an equilibrated system at 10 K, all systems were cooled down to the target temperature in steps of ~ 50 K, controlling the variation of the DSB structure at each step. For tetradecane, the cooling rate turned out to be too fast, and the system frozen in a meta-stable glassy configuration, with the inter-ring dihedral being "blocked" in a out-of-equilibrium position. Two different cooling routes were devised for the DSB/tetradecane system, as sketched in Figures S4 and S5. Following the first cooling route (**Route I**), the tetradecane solvent is first

Figure S4: Cooling route I

cooled down from 293 to 70 K in steps of 30-50 K. During all runs, the geometry of the DSB molecule was kept frozen in the QM optimized structure. Thereafter, all constraints on DSB structure were released, and the whole system was cooled down first to 50 K and successively to 10 K. The second cooling route (**Route 2**) consists in a series of parallel NPT runs, each carried out starting from a set of five uncorrelated configurations extracted from the run at the higher

Figure S5: Cooling route II

temperature. According to the scheme displayed in Figure S5, the final statistic is computed as an ensemble average over 100 uncorrelated runs carried out at 10 K.

The variation of the DSB internal structure upon cooling was monitored along the equilibration trajectories and displayed in Figure S6. For both dihedrals, the fluctuations obtained at 10 K with route II are always larger than the ones found for route I suggesting that Route I should better represent the real thermal oscillations, whereas route II seems to be “trapped” in the starting conformer, which was though populated at higher temperatures.

In the top panel of Figure S7 the total solvent (tetradecane) interaction energy (per molecule) is considered for the two routes upon cooling. Route I leads to slightly more stable values. In the bottom panel the DSB-tetradec. interaction energy (solvation) is displayed along the cooling sequence. It is evident that Route I leads to a better solvated dye, in particular below 70 K, where the solute is allowed to relax from the starting QM geometry.

2PV@tetradecane
2PV dihedral distribution upon cooling

Figure S6: Distribution of flexible (δ , around σ C-C bonds) and stiff (ϕ , around π C=C bonds) dihedrals, defined in Figure S1, of DSB molecule in its ground and excited state upon cooling.

Figure S7: DSB-tetradecane interaction energies upon cooling according to the two cooling routes.

C Additional details on the spectroscopic simulation

C.1 Electronic transition

Table S12: CC bond lengths corresponding to the polyenic chains in DSB and values of the dihedral angles.

Functional	C-C Outer			C=C			C-C Inner		
	S0	S1	Δ	S0	S1	Δ	S0	S1	Δ
PBE0	1.462	1.432	0.030	1.348	1.384	-0.036	1.459	1.419	0.040
CAM-B3LYP	1.469	1.435	0.034	1.341	1.382	-0.041	1.467	1.415	0.051
M06-2X	1.470	1.435	0.034	1.341	1.382	-0.041	1.467	1.417	0.050
ω B97-XD	1.471	1.436	0.035	1.342	1.383	-0.041	1.469	1.417	0.052
M11	1.476	1.440	0.036	1.340	1.382	-0.042	1.474	1.417	0.056

Figure S8: HOMO and LUMO orbitals of DSB computed with CAM-B3LYP. The orbitals computed with PBE0 are practically coincident. The HOMO \rightarrow LUMO transition has a relative weight of 93% with CAM-B3LYP and 99% with PBE0.

C.2 Relaxed scans over flexible torsions

Figure S9: Energy profiles over the torsion around single C-C bonds in the ground (S0, bottom panels) and excited (S1, upper panels) states computed with CAM-B3LYP and PBE0. For some cases, the profiles are also computed with M06-2X, M11 and ω B97XD. The profiles evaluated with MP2 in S0 and ADC(2) in S1 (on TD CAM-B3LYP structures) are also included.

C.3 Benchmark of functional against lineshapes

Figure S10: Absorption and emission relative lineshape spectra in gas phase at 10 and 300 K computed with the VH model projecting out the torsions δ_1 and δ_2 from the vibrational space. The spectra are broadened with a Gaussian profile having HWHM=0.03 eV (at 10 K) or 0.06 eV (at 300 K). The simulations are obtained with PBE0, CAM-B3LYP, M06-2X, ω B97XD and M11 functionals and shifted to better match the experimental spectrum, measured in EPA.

C.4 Additional test on the static vibronic spectra

To account for the effect of torsion in our simulated spectra, we initially assume that the torsional motion is decoupled from the stiff harmonic degrees of freedom. In this framework, the global spectrum arises from the convolution of the spectral shapes obtained for the harmonic modes and that of the yield by the torsional. The latter can be further considered a Gaussian-shaped profile, which will be added to other broadening sources such as the inhomogeneous solvent effect. The broadening of the Gaussian is thus treated as a tunable parameter, adjusted to closely resemble the experimental data [7]. For our simulations, we utilized a Gaussian profile with a half-width at half-maximum (HWHM) of 0.03 eV at 10 K and 0.06 eV at 300 K, both for absorption and emission. The resulting spectra, including simulations with CAM-B3LYP,

PBE0, M06-2X, ω B97XD, and M11 functionals, are depicted in Figure S15.

The broadening induced by the torsional motion can be estimated by examining the distribution of transition energies across the conformational space spanned by the torsions, while keeping the remaining degrees of freedom relaxed [8]. In practice, considering that torsions can be generally described classically, we compute the distributions by adopting classical (Boltzmann) sampling to determine the populations of each conformation. Assuming each torsion to be independent, we obtain distributions for each of the four 1D torsions from the relaxed scans over S0 and S1, and subsequently convolute them to obtain the global distribution. The HWHM values obtained for emission (Boltzmann sampling on S1) at 300 K are 0.072 eV (with CAM-B3LYP) and 0.056 eV (with PBE0), both of which are in close agreement with the empirical value of 0.06 eV adopted in Figure S15. However, the scenario for absorption (sampling on S0) is significantly different, with HWHM values of 0.208 eV (with CAM-B3LYP) and 0.148 eV (with PBE0). Both of these values are considerably larger than the one used in Figure S15. Consequently, such broadening would result in an overly wide spectrum, suggesting that an approach based on this potential energy surface will inevitably lead to excessively large absorption spectra.

This incorrect result actually arises from the combination of a too-flat potential associated with the torsions on S0 and the considerable steepest potential on S1, which also makes the results extremely sensitive to small variations in the description of the surfaces. In this work, electronic structure calculations are carried out adopting (TD)DFT, which may find some difficulties to deal with polyenic systems[?]. Indeed, already in the ground state, recomputing the energy at MP2 level along the relaxed structures evaluated with CAM-B3LYP leads to a profile which, despite still being rather flat, shows the minima more deviated from planarity (of $\sim 25^\circ$), as compared with our DFT results, in agreement with the optimized values reported in the literature [9]. The changes in the excited state when recomputing the energies at ADC(2) level seem even more relevant. Concretely, we found that the energies recomputed with ADC(2)/SV(P) along the TDDFT scan result in flatter profiles in the excited state, which would eventually result in a narrower distribution of vertical energies consequently reducing the broadening induced by the torsions.

Figure S11: Absorption spectra of DSB simulated at 10 K with AH model (both in Cartesian, AH, and internal, AHint, coordinates) and VH model (in internal coordinates). The spectra are broadened with a Gaussian profile having HWHM=0.01 eV. The simulations are obtained with CAM-B3LYP (middle panel) and PBE0 (lower panel) functionals.

D Additional details in the application of the AdMD|gVH method

D.1 Selection of the flexible coordinates

Once a set of 100 snapshots is extracted from the MD simulations and the S0 and S1 energies, gradients and Hessians are computed at the QM/MM level for each one, the selection of the soft coordinates that should be removed from the harmonic set becomes a critical step. All solvent coordinates are removed and, regarding the solute, it is evident from the above discussions that all torsions around single bonds should also be projected out. These torsions are defined as a linear combination, with equal weights, of all dihedral angles which central atoms describe the rotated bond. The validity of the method can be assessed by inspecting the frequencies arising from the vibrational analyses on both the ground and excited states. Namely, we should ensure that all frequencies related to the degrees of freedom retained at a harmonic level are real. The projection of the torsion do reduce the number of imaginary frequencies compared to the vibrational analysis carried out with all solute DoFs, but a significant number of snapshots

Figure S12: Absorption spectra of DSB simulated at 300 K with AH model (both in Cartesian, AH, and internal, AHint, coordinates) and VH model (in internal coordinates). The spectra are broadened with a Gaussian profile having HWHM=0.01 eV. The simulations are obtained with CAM-B3LYP (middle panel) and PBE0 (lower panel) functionals.

Figure S13: Emission spectra of DSB simulated at 10 K with AH model (both in Cartesian, AH, and internal, AHint, coordinates). The spectra are broadened with a Gaussian profile having HWHM=0.01 eV. The simulations are obtained with CAM-B3LYP (middle panel) and PBE0 (lower panel) functionals.

Figure S14: Emission spectra of DSB simulated at 300 K with AH model (both in Cartesian, AH, and internal, AHint, coordinates). The spectra are broadened with a Gaussian profile having HWHM=0.01 eV. The simulations are obtained with CAM-B3LYP (middle panel) and PBE0 (lower panel) functionals.

show a few imaginary frequencies. A close inspection reveals that such persistent imaginary frequencies are related to some flexibility related to the dihedrals around single CC bonds, namely some pyramidalization around the C atoms of the double bonds. It is important to note that our method does not assume a given set of flexible degrees of freedom during the sampling, and such a selection can be done after analysing the flexibility along the trajectory. In this case, it becomes clear that the pyramidalization should also be projected out. To this end, we projected out the four improper dihedrals involved in these pyramidalizations. In the new reduced harmonic space, no imaginary frequencies arise in the vibronic analysis of either the ground or excited state. It should be recalled that all such 12 coordinates (along with solvent coordinates), are treated at a classical level in our procedure.

Figure S15: Absorption and emission relative lineshape spectra in gas phase at 10 and 300 K computed with the VH model projecting out the torsions δ_1 and δ_2 from the vibrational space. The spectra are broadened with a Gaussian profile having HWHM=0.01 eV. The simulations are obtained with PBE0, CAM-B3LYP, M06-2X, ω B97XD and M11 functionals.

Figure S16: Absorption lineshape spectra in gas phase at 300 K computed with the VH model projecting out the torsions δ_1 and δ_2 from the vibrational space on the equilibrium structure and at 3 structures generated by displacing the flexible torsions at arbitrary values (reachable at room temperature) and then relaxing the rest of degrees of freedom. The values of dihedral angles for the flexible torsions at each displaced conformation are given in degrees as $(\delta_1, \delta_1', \delta_2, \delta_2')$.

D.2 Further analysis of the causes of the discrepancies between observed and computed spectral shapes

Despite the very encouraging replication of the experimental trends reported in the main text, the computed absorption spectra are, in general, too broad with respect to the experimental counterparts. In principle, this might be due to two general factors: (i) too long progressions along the quantum high-frequency modes or (ii) an excessive estimate of the broadening effect due to the flexible torsions. The first possibility is ruled out by the fact that the static spectra at 10 K, obtained by removing the effect of the torsions, are in very good agreement with the experiment. This conclusion is corroborated by an analysis with a very simplistic model in which torsions and high-frequency modes are not coupled. In this limit, the shape induced by the torsions and the high-frequency modes can be simply convoluted. As shown in Figure S15, treating the torsional contribution as a Gaussian broadening, with a width tuned phenomenologically, it is indeed possible to find the right HWHM (of 0.03 eV at 10 K and 0.06 eV at 300 K,) to get a nice agreement with experiments (things that would be more difficult if the contribution of the high-frequency modes is intrinsically wrong).

Although the model of independent torsions and high-frequency modes is too simplified – Figure S16 shows that actually different torsional rotations can lead to quite different vibronic profiles along high-frequency modes– it can be exploited further to better individuate the origin of the discrepancy between experiments and computations. In fact, abandoning the simple phenomenological approach, the torsional contribution can be estimated by examining the distribution of transition energies across the conformational space spanned by the torsions, while keeping the remaining degrees of freedom relaxed [8, 10]. In practice, considering that torsions can be generally described classically, we compute the distributions by adopting classical (Boltzmann) sampling to determine the populations of each conformation. Assuming each torsion to be independent, we obtain distributions for each of the four 1D torsions from the relaxed scans over S_0 and S_1 , and subsequently convolute them to obtain the global distribution. Since the 1D distributions are well represented by decaying exponentials, [11] we first fit the distributions to decaying exponential pulses and subsequently compute their convolution (see next section for additional details). The convolution of the four exponentials is then assimilated to

a Gaussian, characterized by its HWHM. This approach is simplified but it has the benefit of providing an estimate of the torsion-induced broadening that directly reflects the shape of the energy profiles. The HWHM values obtained for emission (Boltzmann sampling on S_1) at 300 K is 0.031 eV which is consistent with the empirical value of 0.06 eV reported above (that would also include additional solvent induced broadening). However, the scenario for absorption (sampling on S_0) is significantly different, with an HWHM values of 0.108 eV. Consequently, such broadening would result in an overly wide spectrum, suggesting that an approach based on this potential energy surface will inevitably lead to excessively large absorption spectra.

D.2.1 Estimation of broadening induced by torsions at classical level

In order to estimate the broadening induced by the torsions we first compute the distribution of vertical energies associated to each torsion, following the steps:

1. Compute the relaxed scans for each torsion at S_0 and S_1 . In order to increase the number of points to be used in the following steps, an interpolation is performed.
2. From the relaxed scans, compute vertical energies at each position as $E_v = E_{S_1} - E_{S_0}$
3. Compute the Boltzmann weights along the torsion from the S_0 (for OPA) or S_1 (for EMI) relaxed scans
4. Compute the distribution of vertical energies as a weight histogram of vertical energies with weights computed at step 3
5. Since we observe that the distributions are close to decaying exponentials, the distribution is fitted to such a function

The results of these procedure leads to the distributions (and corresponding fittings) shown in Figure S17.

Figure S17: Distributions of vertical energies for each torsion (corresponding to torsions $\delta 1$ or $\delta 2$) at 300 K for both OPA and EMI transitions.

Assuming that torsions are independent, the final lineshape corresponding to the fluctuations of all of them can be obtained by convoluting their distributions (we have a total of four torsions in DSB: two δ_1 and two δ_2). The convolutions of decaying exponential *pulses* are analytical. For instance, for two decaying exponentials starting at $\omega = 0$ we have:

$$L_2(\omega) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} l_a(\omega') l_b(\omega - \omega') d\omega' = \int_0^{\omega} e^{a\omega'} e^{b(\omega - \omega')} d\omega' \quad (1)$$

where we have adjusted the integration limits including only the region where both functions are non-zero. The solution depends on whether a and b are the same or not:

$$L_2(\omega) = \begin{cases} \omega e^{-a\omega} & (\text{if } a = b) \\ (b - a)^{-1} (e^{-a\omega} - e^{-b\omega}) & (\text{if } a \neq b) \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

By iteratively applying the convolution for two decaying exponentials with the same exponent ($a = b$) plus two additional exponentials with the same exponent ($c = d$), we arrive to the expression of the final lineshape arising from the torsions:

$$L(\omega) = l_a(\omega) * l_a(\omega) * l_c(\omega) * l_c(\omega) = \frac{\omega(e^{-a\omega} + e^{-c\omega})}{(c - a)^2} - \frac{2(e^{-a\omega} - e^{-c\omega})}{(c - a)^3} \quad (3)$$

Using the above expression, the convoluted lineshapes for OPA and EMI at 300 K are shown in Figure S18. From this representation, we obtain a HWHM of 0.108 eV for OPA and 0.035 eV for EMI.

Figure S18: Torsional contribution to the absorption lineshapes obtained by convoluting the transition energy distributions for each torsion at 300 K for OPA and EMI.

D.2.2 On the accuracy of the computed energy profiles for torsions

The results reported in the previous sections clearly indicate that the overestimation of the broadening predicted by our model directly arise from the combination of a too-flat potential associated with the torsions on S_0 and the considerably steeper potential on S_1 , which also makes the results extremely sensitive to small variations in the description of the surfaces. In this work, for computational feasibility, we relied on DFT and TD-DFT (adopting CAM-B3LYP functional) electronic structure methods to compute S_0 and S_1 torsional profiles. A spy that they may be inaccurate already comes from the fact that as already shown years ago in ref. [11], using "effective frequencies" obtained from experiment one would obtain a more reasonable estimate of the broadening. To further inquire the accuracy of CAM-B3LYP predictions, we recomputed at MP2 level the energy profiles on S_0 along the relaxed structures evaluated with CAM-B3LYP (Figure S9 of this SI). The new profiles, despite still being rather flat, are characterized by minima with larger deviations from planarity (of $\sim 25^\circ$), as compared with our DFT results, consistent with the optimized values reported in the literature [9] at MP2/SV(P) level of theory. Moreover, we recomputed the excited-state profiles adopting ADC(2) and found differences which are even more relevant. Concretely, we found that the energies recomputed with ADC(2)/SV(P) along the TDDFT scan resulted in flatter profiles in the excited state.

We have checked that using the MP2 scans for S_0 and the ADC(2) recomputed energies over the TD CAM-B3LYP scan for S_1 , the shapes of the 1D distributions change significantly (due to the double-well potential at S_0), but the global broadening remains quite similar, with HWHM around 0.1 eV. Assuming that CAM-B3LYP is accurate for the ground state and therefore computing the broadening using CAM-B3LYP for S_0 and those recomputed at ADC(2) for S_1 , the resulting HWHM is significantly lower, around 0.06 eV, which agrees pretty well with our phenomenological estimations (see Fig. S15). The variability of these predictions highlights that the accuracy of the potentials computed with standard electronic structure theory methods may be not sufficient to get accurate estimate of such broadening.

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